

Frequency of Abdominal Tuberculosis in Patients presenting with Acute Abdomen

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Dr. Abdur Rehman Alvi**-Consultant Surgeon (FCPS, FRCS, FACS) ⁽²⁾ **Dr. Mobeen Adnan**-Senior Registrar (FCPS G. Surgery) ⁽³⁾ **Dr. Farhan Tahir**-Post Graduate Resident G. Surgery (FCPS).

Abstract

Tuberculosis is an important cause of morbidity throughout the globe. Abdominal Tuberculosis is a great mimicker and is difficult to diagnose. This prospective observational study is based on those patients who were diagnosed to be suffering from Abdominal Tuberculosis only after they presented with an acute abdomen. This study aims to document the frequency of abdominal tuberculosis in patients presenting with an acute abdomen in a tertiary care hospital.

Patients of age 15-80 years of either gender present with acute abdomen (as per operational definition) ASA I & II have been included while patients with chronic liver disease (AST>40IU, ALT>40IU), chronic kidney disease (creatinine >12mg/dl or on hemodialysis) and abdominal trauma both blunt and penetrating (on clinical examination) were excluded. A sample size of 140 cases is calculated with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error and taking an expected percentage of ATB i.e. 10% in patients presenting with acute abdomen.

Keywords: *Abdominal tuberculosis with acute abdomen, Acute presentations of abdominal tuberculosis*

Background

The acute abdomen is a sudden, severe abdominal pain of unclear etiology that is <24 hours in duration. It is in many cases a medical emergency, requiring an urgent and specific diagnosis. Several causes need surgical treatment.

Abdominal Tuberculosis includes tuberculosis infection of the gastrointestinal tract, mesentery, lymph nodes, and omentum, the peritoneum and related solid organs such as liver and spleen. The initial clinical presentations are nonspecific as the disease involves multiple sites with different morphology. No single laboratory investigation is pathognomonic. Radiology often fails to reveal the classical changes described in surgical textbooks.

Abdominal pain is a common presentation in the outpatient setting and is challenging to diagnose. Abdominal pain is the presenting complaint in 1.5% of office-based visits and in 5% of emergency department visits. Although most abdominal pain is benign, as many as 10% of patients in the emergency department setting and a lesser percentage in the outpatient setting have a severe or life-threatening cause or require surgery.

Abdominal Tuberculosis includes tuberculosis infection of the gastrointestinal tract, mesentery, lymph nodes, and omentum, the peritoneum and related solid organs such as liver and spleen. It can have a varied presentation, frequently mimicking other common and rare diseases. TB of the gastrointestinal tract is the sixth most frequent form of the extra-pulmonary site, after lymphatic, genitourinary, bone and joint, miliary and meningeal tuberculosis.

One study has found that the frequency of ATB was 10% on surgical and histopathological findings among cases of acute abdomen. A Yemen study reported the incidence of ATB in 15.5% cases who presented with acute abdomen. In a local study, the frequency of ATB was found in 16% of cases of acute abdomen. But one study has reported the frequency of ATB high as compared to previous studies i.e. 71% of patients in which histopathological culture was positive for Mycobacterium tuberculosis or acid-fast bacilli.

The rationale of this study is to find the frequency of abdominal tuberculosis in patients presenting with an acute abdomen in a tertiary care hospital. In routine, we observed that ATB is a common complication of the acute abdomen but controversial results have been reported in studies above. So we want to confirm whether ATB is commonly present or its frequency can be negligible in a local setting. Moreover, it can help in determining first-line management options when a patient presents in an emergency setting. This will help us to improve our practice and knowledge.

Material and Methods

This is a cross sectional study performed in the Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Gujranwala for six months using Non Probability, Consecutive sampling technique.

2.1 Sample Size

A sample size of 140 cases is calculated with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error and taking an expected percentage of ATB i.e. 10% in patients presenting with acute abdomen.

2.2 Inclusion Criteria

Patients of age 15-80 years of either gender present with the acute abdomen (as per operational definition) ASA I & II

2.3 Exclusion Criteria:

Patients with chronic liver disease (AST>40IU, ALT>40IU), chronic kidney disease (creatinine >12mg/dl or on hemodialysis) and Abdominal trauma both blunt and penetrating (on clinical examination)

Demographic information including name, age, gender, and symptoms of the acute abdomen will also be noted. Then patients will undergo laparotomy under general anesthesia by a single surgical team for exploration of cause of acute abdomen. All the samples will be sent to the laboratory of the hospital for the assessment of abdominal tuberculosis. Reports will be assessed and abdominal tuberculosis will be noted (as per operational definition).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data will be entered and analysed through in SPSS version 20. Quantitative variables like age will be presented as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative variables like gender, symptoms of acute abdomen and abdominal tuberculosis will be presented as frequency and percentage. Data will be stratified for age (40-60, 61-80years), gender (male / female) and different symptoms of the acute abdomen at the time of presentation. Post stratification, Chi-Square test will be applied to compare abdominal tuberculosis in stratified groups. P-value \leq 0.05 will be taken as significant.

3.0 Results

Mean age of patients in this study was 48.04 \pm 18.78 years. Minimum and maximum age of patients was 15 and 80 years respectively. (Table-1)

TABLE-1 - AGE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

<i>n</i>	140
<i>Mean</i>	48.04
<i>SD</i>	18.78
<i>Minimum</i>	15
<i>Maximum</i>	80

Gender distribution of patients showed that there were 57(40.71%) male and 83(59.29%) female patients included in the study. (Figure-1)

FIGURE-1- GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

There were 35(25%) patients who presented with pain, 22(15.7%) patients presented with tenderness and 83(59.3%) patients presented with both symptoms pain as well as with tenderness. (Table-2)

TABLE-2 - FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION FOR SYMPTOMS OF ACUTE ABDOMEN

<i>Symptoms</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Pain</i>	35	25%
<i>Tenderness</i>	22	15.7%
<i>Pain + Tenderness</i>	83	59.3%
<i>Total</i>	140	100%

Abdominal tuberculosis was diagnosed in 24(17.1%) patients. (Table-3)

TABLE-3 - FREQUENCY OF ABDOMINAL TUBERCULOSIS

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Present</i>	24	17.1%
<i>Absent</i>	116	82.9%
<i>Total</i>	230	100%

The most frequent age group of patients in which abdominal tuberculosis was diagnosed was 15-30 years (41.7%) followed by >60 years (29.2%) aged patients followed by 46-60 years (20.8%) aged patients and 31-45 years (8.3%) aged patients. (Table-4)

TABLE-4 - FREQUENCY OF ABDOMINAL TUBERCULOSIS IN RELATION TO AGE GROUPS OF CARE GIVERS

<i>Age Groups</i>	<i>Abdominal Tuberculosis</i>		<i>Total</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<i>15-30</i>	10(41.7%)	24(20.7%)	34
<i>31-45</i>	2(8.3%)	31(26.7%)	33
<i>46-60</i>	5(20.8%)	24(20.7%)	29
<i>>60</i>	7(29.2%)	37(31.9%)	44
<i>Total</i>	24	116	140

Chi-Square Test= 6.504 (p-value= 0.090)

Among the diagnosed patients of abdominal tuberculosis 9(37.5%) were male patients and 15(62.5%) were female patients. However, no statistically significant association was seen between abdominal tuberculosis and gender of patients. i.e. (p-value=0.725) (Table-5)

TABLE-5 - FREQUENCY OF ABDOMINAL TUBERCULOSIS IN RELATION TO GENDER OF CARE GIVERS

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Abdominal Tuberculosis</i>		<i>Total</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
<i>Male</i>	9(37.5%)	48(41.4%)	57
<i>Female</i>	15(62.5%)	68(58.6%)	83
<i>Total</i>	24	116	140

Chi-Square Test= 0.124 (p-value= 0.725)

Among the diagnosed patients of abdominal tuberculosis, the most frequent symptoms were pain along with tenderness (50%) followed by pain(33.3%) and tenderness (16.7%) alone. Abdominal tuberculosis was not significantly associated with any of the presenting complaints of the patients. i.e. (p-value=0.537)(Table-6)

TABLE-6 - FREQUENCY OF ABDOMINAL TUBERCULOSIS IN RELATION TO SYMPTOMS OF ACUTE ABDOMEN

Symptoms	Abdominal Tuberculosis		Total
	Yes	No	
Pain	8(33.3%)	27(23.3%)	35
Tenderness	4(16.7%)	18(15.5%)	22
Pain+Tenderness	12(50%)	71(61.2%)	83
Total	24	116	140

Chi-Square Test= 1.243 (*p-value*= 0.537)

4.0 Discussion

Abdominal tuberculosis is reported from a number of countries. It is also an important health problem in Pakistan. It has various modes of presentation and a high index of suspicion is required for its diagnosis. Abdominal Tuberculosis includes tuberculosis infection of the gastrointestinal tract, mesentery, lymph nodes, and omentum, the peritoneum and related solid organs such as liver and spleen.

The initial clinical presentations are nonspecific as the disease involves multiple sites with different morphology. No single laboratory investigation is pathognomonic. Radiology often fails to reveal the classical changes described in surgical textbooks. Bacterial culture and tissue histopathology through confirmatory are time consuming, and immunological tests though rewarding are expensive.

Moreover, ATB with an acute abdomen presents an enormous challenge to the surgeon. A surgeon has to rely on his clinical judgment and surgical acumen to determine the extent of surgical management in an unprepared, physiologically compromised patient in the emergency setting. While providing surgical care, the surgeon has to collect sufficient pathological tissue for histopathology and microbiology to overcome the diagnostic dilemma.

In this study frequency of abdominal tuberculosis in patients who presented with acute abdomen was 17.1% (24/230). The most frequent symptoms with which patients presents was pain with tenderness (59.3%). Frequency of abdominal tuberculosis was high in the age group 15-30 years followed by >60 years, 46-60 years and 31-45 years. Frequency of abdominal tuberculosis was high among females patients i.e. 62.5% female vs. 37.5% male.

Arunima Mukhopadhyay in his study reported the frequency of abdominal tuberculosis as 10% in patients who presented with acute abdomen. Another local study from Pakistan reported abdominal tuberculosis as 6% in patients presenting with acute abdomen.

Gamal G. Shimy in his study reported that among 90 patients who presented with acute abdomen among these patients 14 (15.5%) had abdominal tuberculosis on the basis of operative findings and histopathological results. A local study from Larkana reported the prevalence of Intestinal Tuberculosis in cases of Acute abdomen as 16%.

Kerry A. Burke in his study highlighted the difficulties encountered in diagnosing ATB. Microbiological culture of biopsy specimens was positive for M. tuberculosis or acid-fast bacilli in 26 (71%) patients.

Above mentioned studies quoted from the literature on the frequency of abdominal tuberculosis showed low frequency. Similarly in this study frequency of abdominal tuberculosis in patients presenting with acute abdomen was also low which is in line with the studies discussed before.

However study of Kerry A. Burke reported a higher frequency of 71% which might be due to some methodological differences or difference in study design as the study was retrospective. Another possible reason may be that ATB is an increasing problem in the UK. This may be a consequence of increased migration from endemic areas and an increasing prevalence of HIV.

Arunima Mukhopadhyay in his study showed female predominance (Female: Male=5:3) and showed that abdominal tuberculosis is predominantly a disease of young adults with females being affected at an earlier age. These facts bear a marked similarity to the findings mentioned in the literature reviewed. In this study, the same trend of female dominance was seen as that reported by Arunima Mukhopadhyay and other studies in the literature.

Tuberculosis is a disease affecting the young population with an average age of 20 – 40 years with an increased incidence in females. The highest frequency of abdominal tuberculosis was seen in the younger age group in this study which is consistent with the other studies in literature who reported the same age range for patients of abdominal tuberculosis presenting with acute abdomen.

Patients with abdominal tuberculosis present with constitutional symptoms of fever, malaise, abdominal pain and altered bowel habits in the early stage of the disease. If not diagnosed early, this leads to complications like intestinal mass, malabsorption, intestinal obstruction or intestinal perforation requiring emergency surgery.

The different modes of presentation as mentioned earlier with their relative frequencies of incidence closely resemble the presentations reported in other series. Though all patients presented with symptoms & signs of acute abdomen, all of them also complained of low grade fever, weight loss, anorexia, disturbed bowel habits, abdominal distension, menstrual abnormalities over a variable period of several weeks to months. Symptoms and signs have been reported similarly by other authors with variable percentages of prevalence.

Acute abdominal condition is one of the most common emergencies in the trauma room, and acute abdominal tuberculosis is one of the common causes of acute abdomen in endemic areas as Intestinal tuberculosis is a common extrapulmonary Manifestation of tuberculosis. Its incidence is increasing in urban and rural areas due to poverty, undernutrition, and overcrowding, Intestinal, and abdominal tuberculosis is a systemic disease. Early diagnosis is the key factor in avoiding systemic and local complications of intestinal tuberculosis, and Antituberculous therapy remains the mainstay of treatment after the surgery as early as possible surgical interference in acute abdominal TB is important to decrease the prevalence of morbidity and mortality in the patients.

Conclusion

The frequency of abdominal tuberculosis in patients presenting with acute abdomen was low still it constitutes a major health problem in our country and presents a diagnostic dilemma and challenge due to various presentations of patients with vague abdominal pain and nonspecific physical findings. The disease is slightly more common adult and middle age females.

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